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Students' self-perceptions with respect to learning through games

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Executive Summary

The UPSKILLS project aims to enhance transferable skills and knowledge within the language domain for modern linguists and language technology students.

This report presents a review of the literature surrounding the efficacy of using games as a pedagogical resource at higher education to facilitate the acquisition of skills that are essential in today's technology-driven society, alongside exploring student perceptions of game-based learning. The investigation which is described in this report highlights some of the factors which students perceive as being influential for the effectiveness of game-based learning for Language and Linguistics Studies in Higher Education. The focal point of the analysis revolves around the integration of games in the curriculum to gauge their impact on student engagement and learning outcomes.

To assess the impact of incorporating games into course materials, a survey tool was created and disseminated among students who were exposed to this novel approach. The survey seeks to capture student opinions on the effectiveness of employing games as a conduit for interacting with the learning content. The analysis of survey responses offers insights into the degree to which students actively engage with the games and whether this engagement transcends mere gameplay to encompass genuine comprehension of the subject matter.

Moreover, the research employs a qualitative methodology, employing focus group interviews. Thematic analysis of this qualitative data revealed two overarching themes that bear significance in the context of integrating game-based learning into higher education.

This report highlights the potential of game-based learning in promoting student engagement and skill acquisition, particularly in the field of Language and Linguistics Studies. Its outcomes underscore the value of innovative pedagogical approaches and offer recommendations for the integration of game-based learning into higher education curricula. As modern education continues to evolve, this study serves as a valuable resource for educators and institutions seeking to harness the benefits of technology-enhanced learning to cultivate proficient and engaged language professionals with skills that are relevant to today's AI-centric society.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
HE	Higher Education
GBL	Game-Based Learning

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1. Introduction

Diverse research suggests that games and gamification offer effective strategies for advancing and enriching learning across various educational settings and levels. In Higher Education (HE), several case studies have been documented, illustrating numerous ways in which games can bolster the learning experience (Crocco et al. 2016; García-Viola et al. 2019; Cabrera-Solano, 2022; Jääskä et al. 2022; Xinogalos & Eleftheriadis, 2023).

Among these, there are heightened levels of student engagement and participation. Games have demonstrated a capacity to facilitate the cultivation of social and emotional learning by transferring valuable soft skills related to effective communication and management of peer interactions (Gee, 2013; de Freitas, 2018). Moreover, they have been observed to increase students' motivation to learn, especially when driven to complete missions or quests presented within the gaming context (Jääskä et al. 2022; Zhao et al. 2022). This, in turn, at times facilitates and supports the exploration of novel ideas or topics, thus fostering deeper learning whilst experiencing a sense of enjoyment and immersion through the gaming environment.

These studies also highlight the potential of games to drive active engagement in the learning process. Complex concepts may be distilled into accessible learning experiences through the game narrative, thus augmenting the possibility of increased participation (Gee, 2007; Gee, 2013). In summary, there is ample research to support the theory that games can indeed serve as platforms through which complex problems are presented to learners in a way that makes them engage more effectively with the content, thus increasing their motivation to increase their knowledge in the field.

1.1 Background and rationale

In an era characterised by rapid technological progress, employing the conventional teacher-centred approach to education could pose challenges in effectively engaging students. At HE, students view assessment as an important component of their learning process (Murillo-Zamorano et al. 2021). As more AI tools are emerging, aiding assessment tasks such as written reports, assignments and various projects, learners might lack the incentive to explore various fields of knowledge in more depth. Investigations into the use of games, serious games, and gamification have consistently demonstrated that participants report increased engagement and a positive shift in their attitude towards learning (Murillo-Zamorano et al. 2021). This increased engagement with the subject matter frequently leads to a more active form of learning.

Mora et al. (2020) claim that by immersing learners in problem-solving activities set within work-related scenarios, and actively involving them in the process, it becomes possible to develop essential skills demanded by today's evolving market. The fundamental principle underpinning active learning is to empower learners to take agency of their learning,

while the teacher assumes the role of a knowledge mediator (Kolb, 1984). Despite the number of advantages of active learning, which includes creative skill development within collaborative settings, HE studies such as those by Guerrero-Roldán & Noguera (2018) reveal that the predominant pedagogical approach among academics remains the passive learner model. Remarkably, a significant number of educators seem to show distrust in the students' abilities to construct their own cognitive frameworks, consequently opting for conventional methodologies for presumed higher quality education (Guerrero-Roldán & Noguera 2018).

Studies also show that the new generation of learners consider this perspective outdated, particularly when it pertains to translating acquired skills from academic settings to real-world employment scenarios. Murillo-Zamorano et al. (2021) have pinpointed the existing gaps in the requirements of the digital society, educators, and students. They propose that incorporating gamification and game-based active learning encounters could indeed address the needs of all three stakeholder categories effectively.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The objectives of this report are the following:

- Review some of the current literature focusing on studies about the effectiveness of gamification and game-based learning (GBL) at HE;
- Utilise a survey tool for collecting student reflections on the use of GBL and in particular focus on the use of one of the games which they have experienced as part of their program of studies;
- Create a set of questions for a semi-structured focus group interview to gather deeper insights into aspects of student considerations regarding GBL;
- Use descriptive analytics as well as thematic analysis to analyse and discuss the results obtained, comparing these to the literature reviewed;
- Discuss the potential impacts of using games and gamification methods with different stakeholders in linguistics and language specialisation at HE level.

1.3 Scope and limitations

The scope of this report is to highlight some of the main findings of the practice-based research that has been going on as part of the UPSKILLS Erasmus+ funded project. The targeted audience are primarily educators, lecturers and academics at HE who wish to take up GBL within their classroom activities. Although the recommendations that are proposed in this report are generalised, these can be further scaled to diverse teaching fields. The theoretical frameworks underpinning these recommendations go beyond the traditional cognitive learning theories, shifting towards the self-learning paradigm, where the learner chooses his/her own learning pathway, assigning meaning to the information that is acquired depending on personal needs and driven by the context of learning.

Some challenges have emerged that may have constrained the outcomes of this study. Initially, it was assumed that teachers or academics would introduce pre-existing games to chosen participants from the target audience throughout the delivery of lectures during the academic year. However, subsequent to a series of consultation meetings, it was determined that the game selection should align with the syllabus being developed by the involved partners. After careful consideration and various technical hurdles obstructing the use of a pre-existing game, it was collectively resolved that a custom serious game reflecting key aspects of linguistics would need to be created. This version of the game was made available during the UPSKILLS summer school, thus the investigation was conducted with the attending students of this program. There were 28 students participating in all and, although they can be seen as a representative cross-section of the intended audience, the findings cannot be statistically analysed for their effectiveness. Hence, the designed tool was tailored to this small sample size, and descriptive analytics were applied as a quantitative assessment. Additionally, a voluntary focus group was formed from the same summer school attendees to gain deeper qualitative insights into the efficacy of GBL.

2. Literature review

HE institutions are in a continuous state of flux as they struggle against competitive markets and the rapid technological advances which are shaping not only the job market, but are having considerable impact on society. Any learning institution which is not going to keep up the momentum which the technological pace and the subsequent needs which this rapid evolution inevitably brings, will risk future sustainability. According to a number of reports one of the solutions to these challenges that HE are currently facing is that of adopting a more active student-centred approach to learning (D'Adamo & Gastaldi, 2023, Rosowski, 2023; Willsea, 2023).

2.1 Active learning in Higher Education

The job market is currently undergoing an unparalleled transformation, often likened to the industrial revolution but on a grander scale. The emergence of AI-powered tools such as Chat-GPT and similar applications using large language models (LLMs) is creating a wave of apprehension among numerous workers whose jobs could be impacted by this technology. This circumstance underscores the urgency for HE institutions to introduce pedagogical approaches that align more closely with contemporary market demands and societal requisites. The conventional teacher-centric instructional models may be viewed as obsolete

and inadequate in addressing the distinct requirements arising from the introduction of these expansive language models.

Active learning is a model of learning which supports student autonomy, initiative and active participation in their own learning processes. The underlying theoretical framework presupposes that the teachers take a more passive role, as mediators of knowledge rather than transmitters of knowledge in the classroom. According to a study by Guerrero-Roldán & Noguera (2018), the trend among universities is that they are still retaining their passive student learning approach. Academics and teachers seem to be of the perspective that the way to transmit knowledge is through teacher-led lectures.

2.2 Game Based Learning projects in Higher Education

A study by Murillo-Zamorano et al (2021) reveals that gamification and a GBL approach may positively impact the skills demanded by society through the active learning approach. In the study the authors hypothesised that gamification may have a positive impact on the skills required by the evolving digital society, as well as a positive impact on academic skills and student satisfaction. There were 132 participants in the study, enrolled in the Macroeconomics module following the Degree in Business Administration and Management at the University of Extremadura, Spain. The methods of study included a quasi-experimental design with 2 groups following an active learning approach, but with one group included a gamified approach to the active learning design process. The results show that the group which participated in the gamified active learning model approach showed a statistically significant positive shift towards the attainment of soft skills such as ability to work in groups, listen to others' opinions, apply knowledge in practice, ability to analyse and synthesise. These are considered to be 21st century digital skills that are applicable to a wide range of jobs at different employment levels. However the study revealed that gamification gave no added value either to academic skills, or to student motivation. The authors also concluded that the use of games and gamification methods offered no hindrance to the attainment of learning targets and academic abilities.

In another study, Zhao et al (2022) used two games from the NEWTON Project¹, namely the 'Variable' and the 'Loop' game to support knowledge acquisition, enhance student experience and investigate the usability of such games as part of a programming course at HE level. The results presented in this case indicate that having targeted games for knowledge acquisition may benefit more an introduction to the learning content rather than to reinforce learned concepts. Results also showed that in terms of the user experience, students' self-evaluation gave an indication that in most cases after playing the two games designed specifically to teach programming only showed a marginal positive increase in the motivation to study programming in more depth. In addition the authors concluded that a degree of

¹ NEWTON PROJECT; EU Horizon 2020 Innovation Action, [Online] Available: <https://www.newtonproject.eu/>

personalisation of gameplay might have benefited the learners more. Although the games presented in this case study focus on the learning content, in this case specific programming activities, they do not involve any specific active learning activities, and they do not target additional skills such as those mentioned by Murillo-Zamorano et al (2021). This lack of inclusion of active learning activities as well as 21st century skills, might have had an effect on the students' responses towards their game user experience.

In summary, both the studies by Murillo-Zamorano et al (2021) and Zhao et al (2022) explore the implications of gamification and game-based learning (GBL) in educational contexts, albeit with varying results and foci. Murillo-Zamorano et al (2021) found that a gamified approach to active learning significantly improved students' 21st-century soft skills like group work, analytical thinking, and practical application of knowledge. However, the study found no significant advantage in terms of academic skills or student motivation. This research underscores the potential for gamification to prepare students for the evolving demands of a digital society. On the other hand, the study by Zhao et al (2022), which employed targeted games within a programming course, found only marginal increases in student motivation. Moreover, the games did not incorporate active learning components or address broader soft skills, which may explain the limited impact on student motivation and experience. Overall, while gamification and GBL show promise for developing critical soft skills essential in today's job market, their impact on academic achievement and motivation appears to be less consistent, calling for more nuanced application and perhaps greater personalisation in educational settings.

3. Methodology

The UPSKILLS project consortium has designed and developed a number of course modules designed and targeted towards a number of different aspects of the study of Linguistics and Language Specialisation at HE. For the purpose of this study three games were specifically designed for the UPSKILLS curriculum; One aimed to reinforce Machine Learning knowledge, one aimed to teach more complex programming concepts, whilst the third one followed a serious game design based on the narrative of the language specialist profile as it follows the experience of an intern in a Research and Development company that specialises in linguistic analysis using digital and NLP methods. The latter, TopLang: An UPSKILLS Simulation Experience, was chosen to be piloted during the UPSKILLS summer school program, based on the results obtained from the initial game preferences survey, as outlined in the report for Intellectual Output 4.1 'Using Educational Games within the Scope of UPSKILLS'.

3.1 Research design

A mixed methods design approach was used to determine the effect of this genre of game on the participants self-reported engagement and overall game-based experience. All participants followed the same game-based experience throughout the summer school program, following which they were asked to complete a self-reflective survey to gauge their impressions. Additionally, some participants volunteered to participate in a focus group session, to provide further insights into their experience.

3.2 Participants

There were 25 participants enrolled in the UPSKILLS Summer School Program and 24 participants agreed to take part in the post-game survey. The participants provided an overall cross-section of the expected demographic for the linguistics specialist profile. 19 out of 24 respondents were in the 18-25 age group, whilst the rest were spread across the different categories from 26-65 years. The participants were briefed before the start of the game-based activity and signed their consent to participate.

Figure 1. Gender of participants in the UPSKILLS summer school program

Figure 2. Age of participating students

Figure 3. Country of residence of participating students

3.3 Survey tool design

3.3.1 Purpose of the survey

The post-game student perception survey was formulated to evaluate participants' comprehensive game-play, encompassing their perceived educational gains and their perception of the game's content design. The survey was divided into two parts: the first part captured insights on the game's design aspects, while the second section aimed to capture participants' holistic game engagement. A three-point Likert Scale was employed to provide a quantifiable measurement of the students' assessment of their game-driven learning experience.

3.3.2 Development of survey questions

The survey questions were developed by loosely adopting question items from the Game Experience Questionnaire (GEQ) tool developed by IJsselsteijn et al. (2013). The questions aimed to give a measure of the engagement with the game content, thus motivating the participants to delve into the content matter in more depth. Högberg et al. (2019), developed and validated an instrument designed to collate the whole gameful experience, which also included elements from the GEQ to determine the level of affect achieved during gameplay. However the instrument developed by Högberg et al. (2019) gave a more holistic measure of all the elements making up the game experience, including the level of competition, flow, immersion, challenge and skill, most of which were not applicable to the UPSKILLS GBL experience.

The survey can be accessed online through [this link](#).

3.3.3 Validation of the Survey Tool

In the research process, the survey tool underwent a validation process to ensure its effectiveness in collecting accurate and reliable data. Initially, the tool was subjected to face validation, where experts in the field reviewed the questions for their relevance, clarity, and

appropriateness in relation to the study's objectives. This step ensured that the survey questions were theoretically sound and logically connected to the research goals.

Following face validation, the survey tool was then tested using convenient samples of respondents, often referred to as pilot testing. This phase served multiple purposes: first, it allowed the researchers to identify any questions that respondents found confusing or unclear. Second, it helped establish the reliability of the answers, as inconsistent responses to the same or similar questions could indicate issues with the survey's internal reliability. Feedback from this sample group was critically analysed to pinpoint questions with errors relating to clarity and reliability.

Based on the findings from both face validation and the pilot testing phase, revisions were made to refine the survey tool. Questions that were identified as problematic were either rephrased for better clarity or removed altogether to enhance the instrument's reliability. This comprehensive validation process aimed to maximise the survey tool's effectiveness in capturing meaningful and reliable data for the study.

3.4 Focus Group Questions

Semi-structured interview questions were designed and administered to a small sample of participants from the summer school program. The scope of the questions were to gain more insights into their thoughts about the game and at the same time, assess the level of engagement which the participants felt they could achieve with such a genre and application of games to their learning. The list of questions that served to initiate discussions in the Focus Group session can be seen in Appendix D. In addition to documenting the research conducted in UPSKILLS, the list of questions used for the focus group serves a dual purpose. Educators and researchers may find this set of questions to be a valuable instrument for their own inquiries into educational practices and student experiences. Therefore, we encourage teachers to consider utilising these questions as a foundation for their own research, thereby broadening the scope and application of the investigative tools developed through UPSKILLS.

3.5 Data collection procedure

The students completed the survey after having played the TopLang game at the UPSKILLS Summer School, held at Petnica Science Centre, Serbia between the 15-20 July 2023. Following the administration of the survey, participants were recruited voluntarily to take part in a focus group to discuss in more depth their post-game reflections, in particular, their thoughts about the role of GBL in HE.

3.6 Ethical considerations

Participants were briefed before the game and before the survey tool was given to them. During the briefing, they were informed that they were free to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. In addition the participants signed a consent form indicating their willingness to participate in the study. The participants' responses were recorded anonymously and all personal data pertaining to their identities was removed after the data was analysed.

4. Results

This section presents the results emergent from the survey tool and the focus group interviews.

4.1 Quantitative Analysis - Self-Reflective Survey

Owing to the small size of the group, descriptive statistical analysis was used to gather insights into the students' perceptions on the learning design of the game they played, as well as their thoughts about the effectiveness of this game in engaging them as learners more deeply with the research aspect of the job of the Linguistics Specialist.

The game which was played during the summer school program was TopLang, a game that was specifically designed for the UPSKILLS project. The game can be launched from the MOODLE platform where the students could also access a number of course modules and units related to UPSKILLS.

23 participants played the game 1-3 times whilst 1 participant played the game 4-6 times. 22 participants played the game for 30 minutes or less whilst 2 participants played the game for 30 minutes to 1 hour in total. 13 out of the 24 participants reached completion of the game.

The subsequent set of questions were related to the learning experience that the participants felt they got from the game. When asked whether they felt that the game was directly related to the course they were studying for, 21 participants responded positively. 20 participants also responded positively to the question asking whether they thought that this game was related to the profession of the language specialist, whilst 3 had neutral opinions and 1 participant thought that the game was not related to the profession of the language specialist. 21 participants also responded positively to the question related to whether this game made them reflect about the profession of the language specialist.

Figure 4. Frequency distribution of the participants' responses towards the learning design of TOPLANG (n=23)

The participants were also asked if they felt that the game they played contributed to enhancing their overall knowledge of the learning material, and whether the game helped them want to learn more about the subject. For these specific questions 1 participant opted out of answering the questions. However, for the rest of the respondents, the results indicate a positive attitude to the game's design of the learning content.

Figure 5. Frequency distribution of participants' perceptions of the game's complexity (n=24)

The second part of the survey tool consisted of questions related to the design of the game in terms of ease of use, and elements of affect related to game play.

The insights drawn from Figure 5 provide a good indication that the game interface's design was not only user-friendly but also succeeded in fostering an enjoyable experience for the participants. The game, according to the participants' survey responses, incorporated entertaining components, and the participants readily embraced the game's narrative. This observation underscores the game's efficacy in not only engaging the players but also in establishing a sense of connection with its storyline.

Figure 6. Frequency distribution of the participants' self-reported game engagement (n=24)

The positive acceptance of the game was substantiated through inquiries that delved into the extent of participants' self-declared engagement. An interesting insight emerged, that the participants not only found the game's storyline intriguing but also felt incentivised to sustain their involvement. Yet, when confronted with the question of whether the game aided in identifying concepts overlooked in lectures, a marginally negative response was registered. This insight unveils a disparity between the game's narrative appeal and its practical alignment with the educational curriculum. Consequently, while the game captured attention and sustained motivation, its integration with the course content was met with certain reservations due to perceived incongruities.

However there was a positive response when participants were asked whether they thought that the game tested their knowledge of the subject with 15 out of 24 participants answering that it was true.

The last section of the survey tool asked 2 open ended questions with the scope of gaining more insights into how the participants would choose to improve the game they experimented with and whether they would be happy to recommend such a game as part of the HE learning experience. 17 out of 24 participants remarked that they would recommend

the use of this game as part of a GBL experience. The rest of the participants did not give any answer.

The list below summarises the improvements that the participants suggest to make TopLang more effective as a game:

1. **Expand Selection Options:** Increase the range of choices at each stage of the game to engage players more deeply.
2. **Enhance Originality:** Move away from a "canned" plot and infuse the storyline with more unique and creative elements.
3. **Diversify Quizzes:** Incorporate various types of quizzes to test different skills and knowledge areas.
4. **Multimedia Integration:** Consider adding animations and visual elements in addition to text boxes for a more immersive experience.
5. **Artwork Quality:** If budget allows, collaborate with an artist to improve the quality of the visuals and make them more engaging.
6. **Increase Difficulty in NLP Track:** Make the Natural Language Processing (NLP) challenges more complex to engage players who are looking for a tougher experience.
7. **Add Skill-Testing Questions:** Include questions or scenarios that actually test the skills of the participant, going beyond simplistic choices like "going to the bar or not."
8. **Heighten Stakes:** Add options that can lead to negative outcomes, making choices more impactful and increasing player investment in the game.
9. **Enhance Interactivity:** Make the game more interactive with additional effects and animations.
10. **Clarify Main Character Skills:** Provide more details about the main character's skills and qualifications to make it clearer whether they are suited for the challenges and opportunities presented in the game.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis - Focus Group

In addition to the survey tool, a group of 8 participants voluntarily agreed to participate in a focus group session which was held online via Zoom. The participants signed a consent form and agreed to a recording of the session for research and documentation purposes.

The focus group session was introduced with a short briefing about the scope of the interview and a roundtable introduction of the participants.

Thematic analysis was conducted by closely examining the transcript of the recording. In the initial phase, a thorough review of the transcript allowed for the identification of two overarching themes. Subsequently, a comprehensive list of codes was formulated, and specific excerpts from the transcript were assigned the relevant codes based on their content.

Figure 7. Thematic analysis of focus group interview

Following the transcript of the discussion spurred by semi-structured interview questions, two main themes emerged from the discussion.

The main theme of **Game Play** featured prominently in most of the discussion. This was further decomposed into 4 sub-themes, namely *Game Genres*, *Competition*, *Conflict* and *Teamwork*.

The participants spoke about the different *Game Genres* they frequently come across, both as gamers as well as learners at HE. Most of the games which they have been exposed to within the HE institutions have involved either quizzes or quiz-based games such as Kahoot!, Quizlet, Mentimeter or Neopod. However since a number of the participants described themselves as gamers, they commented on the possibilities of using different genres for learning. In most of the discussions they either referred to general off-the-shelf commercial games such as *Assassin's Creed*, or else purposely made role-playing (RPG) adventure games with a meaningful narrative.

“I like racing games and for example there are games that are situated in various realistic countries, and when playing these racing games it feels that you are also learning about these countries. I really learned a lot through these games.”

“Many people learned a lot about renaissance just by playing assassins' creed.”

“If such a big project was possible, I would try to make it as much "generalisable" as possible. Maybe having a main storyline about being a researcher, what it means to do research etc. would be a good start. Then one could have side quests or even DLC/expansions about specific subjects that introduce new quests/characters into the game. Something a bit less ambitious would be to use simpler game engines such as GameMaker or RPG Maker. But in general, I would really like to have an element of adventure, maybe in the form of a game where you are a researcher and you go around doing stuff like chasing people for your experiments.”

“On the other hand, if it is a game that could be played on your phone and easily accessible (aka a separate app) it would be an easy go-to while waiting in line or moving in public transportation.”

“Like I said in the interview I am no gamer but when I think of games I don't think of quizzes. Regardless of how crazy it may seem I think that when making educational games one should still keep the entertaining character. I remember L saying that things could be learned as a side quest, so perhaps some theoretical subjects like anthropological linguistics, field linguistics, or forensic linguistics could benefit a lot from presenting their findings as a storyboard of an adventure game.”

The element of *Competition* in games also featured prominently during the discussion. Views were mixed and participants agreed that personalisation might be helpful in this matter. According to the participants, whilst competition might be viewed as increasing motivation for some, for others it may be a cause of stress or pressure thus hindering progress.

“Everything is nice when there is competition but competition may put pressure.”

“Competition but in a safe environment so you're competing with your own progress. Games are valuable to propel yourself and progress the past knowledge.”

“If we play a quiz as a group the competition makes us open to learning together. This sort of environment helps us learn more.”

“I have used offline games in Spanish classes and we worked in groups and it was better cause it was less stress and we could help each other. We had a

treasure hunt and it was fun, but working in groups, helped us solve problems together.”

Participants also brought up the issues of *Conflict* in games during game play. According to them, conflict during play may not necessarily be a bad thing and may even be conducive to learning.

“We were on discord, but there was a bit of conflict. Just a little bit toxic is ok, when it gets too much, then we report. But sometimes you know we say we lost the game because of your fault. So in teamwork game conflict does happen and it's ok. There are people who like teamwork without competitiveness. But then there are people who like the competition.”

“It really depends on what you're teaching. Certain subjects may be better if people play solo, so that people don't depend too much on each other and thus avoid conflict.”

“Also there is a lot of recommendation like usually you need to select the sort of skills you will need or have to learn about, and then there is teamwork. Sometimes it is good to have games where there is conflict, because sometimes conflict is good for learning.”

Teamwork featured mostly in discussions related to competition and conflict. Participants discussed how team work would not only help students acquire soft skills like communication, project management, etc, but it would also give them the confidence which they would sometimes lack especially if they are not familiar with playing games.

“If we play a quiz as a group the competition makes us open to learning together. This sort of environment helps us learn more.”

“Also people can also learn soft skills, so games based on team work, you need to work together and collaborate, and some games based on strategy, and therefore there is a lot to learn from these games.”

“I have used offline games in Spanish classes and we worked in groups and it was better cause it was less stress and we could help each other. We had a treasure hunt and it was fun, but working in groups, helped us solve problems together.”

“If a game is familiar to everyone then everyone can play. But if the game is unknown, then people might not be happy to play.”

“One approach we used was that we were sitting in a room all together whilst playing so we could also ask each other.”

“But in general, I think it would be better to use games as in-class activities if there is the time to do so. It could also be interesting to create something particularly challenging to encourage students to work together to complete the game.”

The second main theme which emerged from the focus group discussion was that of **Assessment**, which could be further divided into two sub-themes, namely *Skills* and *Achievements*.

Whereas in general, there seemed to be an agreement that games can be used for learning at HE, participants were wary of using games as tools for assessment. In their own words, the scope of game is that of offering learners a safe environment where to make mistakes, and learn at their own pace without fear of retribution. In terms of assessment, the participants spoke mostly about the measurement of the participants' *Achievements* as well as the *Skills* that the use of meaningful games can target. Most of the skills which were mentioned referred to the softer skills, and learning was perceived to be as a peripheral outcome of the game play rather than targeted learning with specific curricular content.

“Questions shouldn't be necessarily hard but if you're in a safe environment it's good to make mistakes. Usually you have progress in a game so this constant becomes an increasing challenge.”

“My idea of an educational game would be a game in which participants learn as a side quest. The game is not focused on learning and you learn in the process of doing something totally different.”

“A course-long experience would be great but it's very important to have feedback from the participants and adjust to the needs of the participants.”

“If it's course long it might get to be a tool for grading students and some people might get stressed because they want to get the best, so it becomes a tool for assessment.”

“Also people can also learn soft skills, so games based on team work, you need to work together and collaborate, and some games based on strategy, and therefore there is a lot to learn from these games.”

“Also there is a lot of recommendation like usually you need to select the sort of skills you will need or have to learn about, and then there is teamwork.”

“I think that, as of now, two main areas can benefit from gamified approaches: subjects for which there are already good games available (for example programming), and transversal skills (such as teamwork, project management, learning new things quickly) which can be developed by playing general games as well.”

“Another idea could be to use the game as a tool for teaching, for example by having the students perform a task that requires them to look things up on the internet. I'm not an expert when it comes to teaching but I feel like searching things on your own helps you remember them more effectively.”

5. Discussion

The subsequent section delves into the outcomes attained through the triangulation of data collection methods, specifically the merge of findings from the self-report survey tool administered after gameplay and the insights garnered from the focus group interview.

5.1 Overview of findings

The main findings from this analysis indicate that the game that was presented during the UPSKILLS Summer School was well accepted. Participants found it easy to follow and play, and they reported that the game's storyline was fun to follow. Nonetheless participants felt that the game's quests were not challenging enough, and that more activities could have been included. Graphics and animations were amongst the game elements that were mentioned that could improve the overall game experience of TopLang.

Within the context of the focus group session, a different dimension of GBL was explored. Participants engaged in discourse that revolved around the concept of learning as an indirect consequence of engaging with the game, as opposed to the direct acquisition of knowledge often associated with quiz-based games. This perspective introduced a nuanced viewpoint, suggesting that the process of gameplay itself, along with the intrinsic challenges, decision-making scenarios, and immersive storytelling, could lead to a more holistic and comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Participants hypothesised that this immersive exposure could potentially foster critical thinking skills, team work, lateral

thinking, and a deeper grasp of the overarching concepts, gradually building a more integrated understanding over time. This discussion revealed the multifaceted nature of learning within game-based contexts, highlighting the dynamic interplay between engagement and knowledge acquisition without targeting specific content directly.

5.2 Comparison of Game-Based Learning and traditional instruction

The findings discussed previously, particularly those stemming from the insights garnered during the focus group interviews, align with prior research on GBL. These findings agree with the perspectives presented by scholars such as Gee (2007 & 2013) and de Freitas (2006 & 2018), who expound that games should be perceived as intricate problem-solving scenarios, within which learning unfolds as a product of the immersive engagement cultivated throughout gameplay. This assertion underscores the notion that learning within the realm of GBL is not just the direct assimilation of facts, but rather a holistic process that transcends traditional pedagogical methods.

Studies emergent from scholars such as Pavaloiu, et al. (2016) and Xinogalos & Eleftheriadis, (2023) have collectively advocated for an alternative perspective, wherein the act of navigating challenges, making strategic decisions, and negotiating complex narratives within games fosters a cognitive environment conducive to experiential learning. This immersive and participatory approach, which also aligns to the active learning framework (Kolb, 1984) stands in contrast to conventional teaching methods where knowledge is often transmitted through didactic means. In game-based scenarios, learners actively grapple with scenarios, explore outcomes, and refine strategies, thereby cultivating critical thinking, adaptability, and problem-solving skills that extend beyond the virtual realm (Steinkuehler et al. 2012). The synergy between these insights and the current study's focus group discussions underscores the evolving concept that GBL is a dynamic pathway for nurturing multifaceted skills, often transcending the limitations of traditional educational models. This alignment substantiates the idea that the cultivation of a problem-solving mindset and the emergence of learning within GBL scenarios mirror the broader philosophical frameworks articulated by Kolb (1984).

Recent studies (Tavares, 2022; Grech & Grech, 2021; Crocco et al. 2016) have indicated that, where HE courses have implemented GBL approaches, students report higher levels of engagement and motivation, leading them to deeper learning of the subject. Most of these studies have experimented with GBL within class-based activities, although Jiménez-Rodríguez et al. (2020), have also reported GBL's effectiveness in an eLearning setting.

Tavares (2022) in his systematic review of GBL-related literature has however listed a number of limitations relative to the deployment of GBL approaches at HE level. Some of these limitations included increased levels of student anxiety, especially in time-limited and competitive activities, although García-Viola et al. (2019) have also mentioned that these

specific game elements could give students more motivation and encourage them to work under pressure. These findings resonate with the insights from the participants during the focus group interview who mentioned student anxiety in competitive, pressure-driven game environments, yet at the same time, when administered according to individual learner needs may provide added motivation and excitement for learning.

5.3 Perceived effectiveness of Game-Based Learning in language and linguistics education

Emerging from the UPSKILLS project's quantitative and qualitative analysis, the insights gained, align closely with current literature on the effectiveness of GBL in educational contexts. Participants uniformly acknowledged GBL as a pedagogical tool that aids not just in the acquisition of knowledge, but also in skill development. This is especially pertinent in fostering soft skills like collaboration, communication, and problem-solving, corroborating Tavares' (2022) findings on the impact of the use of games on the learning experience of nursing undergraduate students as well as those of Zhao et al (2022) who investigated the use of game-based learning for programming undergraduate students. The focus group data further illuminated the transformative potential of AI-powered adventure games in fields like linguistics. These games, rich in narrative and decision-making elements, were perceived as invaluable for a deeper, more critical engagement with subject matter. This goes beyond the mere reinforcement of existing knowledge, which is often the primary function of game genres like quizzes.

Parallel to these observations, Jääskä & Aaltonen's (2022) study emphasises that while GBL can significantly increase student engagement and motivation, educators view it as a complement to traditional teaching methods rather than a replacement. They caution that an exclusive reliance on GBL could pose risks to students' cognitive development and overall well-being.

Moreover, the UPSKILLS findings align with Chan & Lo's (2022) study which affirmed the positive reception of gamified learning environments employing tools like Kahoot and Padlet. According to their research, these tools not only enhance student engagement but also facilitate easier assimilation of learning concepts through interactive visuals and active participation.

Overall, the UPSKILLS analysis and corroborating studies substantiate the growing consensus that GBL can indeed enrich educational experiences and aid students in engaging more deeply with the field of study. However, for optimal outcomes, it appears most effective when deployed in tandem with traditional teaching methods, particularly given its potential limitations and risks as identified in the UPSKILLS studies and literature presented.

5.4 Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of Game-based Learning

In a number of studies that present the use of GBL HE, a recurring theme involves the delineation of various challenges and limitations that could potentially impact the effectiveness of this approach. Considering these factors can help in overcoming the challenges that hinder the enhancement of GBL's effectiveness in higher education.

1. Student needs and preferences; many studies such as those by Chan & Lo (2022) and Jääskä & Aaltonen (2022) mention that not all students may be ready to take on GBL or gamified learning environments. Such environments may cause stress and anxiety amongst students who may not enjoy competitive or time-pressure environments. These sentiments were also echoed during the UPSKILLS focus group interview. Therefore it is best for teachers and academics to understand their learners, and personalise the GBL environment according to their audience. One example would be to include teamwork in the GBL method to alleviate some of the pressure, that learners who might be unfamiliar with the game, might feel. Another example would be to remove global leaderboards and personalise achievements to align to the learners' past scores.
2. Briefing and instructions; games and gamified activities ought to be accompanied by comprehensive guidelines and insights outlining how the game aligns with the course curriculum, even if the alignment is approached from a broader perspective. For instance, if an instructor opts to introduce a custom-designed adventure game tailored for the field of anthropological linguistics, strategically targeting cross-cutting skills like project management, teamwork, and adaptability to new contexts, it becomes important to give students a comprehensive overview of the game's overarching purpose and relevance before and after gameplay. The absence of clear instructions and constructive feedback may risk leave some students feeling disoriented, rendering them unable to grasp the underlying rationale behind incorporating a gaming element. Absence of clear guidelines can lead to feelings of frustration, subsequently causing disengagement, rather than motivation. These observations align with the findings underscored by Chan & Lo (2022), reinforcing the significance of transparent communication and context setting to sustain meaningful engagement and learning outcomes.
3. Technology infrastructure; the constraints outlined across various studies (Chan & Lo, 2022 & Höyng, 2022) concerning GBL show how a weak technological infrastructure within the HE environment can result in increased frustration, ultimately impeding the efficacy of GBL initiatives. It's important to recognise that any gamified setting or game reliant on technology-assisted platforms hinges significantly on the robustness of the underlying networks and infrastructure. To illustrate, consider a scenario where the WiFi signal remains feeble and prone to disruptions; under such circumstances, participating in gameplay could rapidly

become unfeasible. Should teachers persist in integrating gaming in class under such conditions, the outcome may inadvertently culminate in students losing enthusiasm for gameplay, a consequence contrary to the intended goal of fostering increased engagement. The sentiment of frustration stemming from the absence of adequate technology was also brought up during the UPSKILLS Focus Group Interview.

5.5 Implications for Language and Linguistics Studies in Higher Education

This report has highlighted a number of considerations pertinent to the integration of games and gamified environments for learning. The findings of this study culminate in a prevailing consensus that the domain of Language and Linguistics studies within Higher Education can benefit substantially from the inclusion of game-based environments. Yet, this consensus does not uniformly advocate for games that exclusively assess knowledge through quiz-based mechanisms. Instead, a prevailing perspective highlights that the use of games transcends simple knowledge assessment and should thus focus on more complex and dynamic learning exchanges. In fact, research corroborates that games featuring intricate mechanics can exert a positive effect on student engagement and motivation, prompting a more immersive and deeper exploration of the subject.

A discussion point that emerged from the UPSKILLS Focus Group interview related to the concept that games, rather than being conduits for knowledge dissemination, can be strategically tailored to cultivate transversal skills. These skills, essential in today's rapidly evolving technology-centric society, become the focus of game-based interventions. Studies show that the strategic integration of GBL in HE has the potential to foster a more dynamic, interactive, and participatory learning paradigm. This transformative approach is conducive to fostering self-initiated learning behaviours and more proactive participation. However, the implementation of this approach necessitates the meticulous design of the GBL environment, engineered with specific learning outcomes in mind. It's equally important for educators, academics, and researchers to cultivate familiarity with diverse genres of games, thus empowering themselves to seamlessly adapt it to their course content, thereby tailoring the experience to the unique needs of their students.

6. Conclusion

The core objective of the UPSKILLS Project was to address the prevailing gaps and discrepancies in skills of graduates in language-related disciplines through the creation of a novel curriculum component and its accompanying resources, intended for integration within ongoing linguistics and language-oriented programs. The project promised a comprehensive, research-driven approach into language-related academic pathways, to support the future

employability of students, empowering them with the essential proficiencies required for an expanded spectrum of roles within the job market.

To this intent, this specific task focused on measuring the self-perception of the effectiveness of using games and gamified approaches in learning programs, specifically designed for language-related academic pathways. The methods adopted for this study included quantitative and qualitative approaches, derived from literature featuring studies on the application of GBL in HE. The insights garnered from this investigation suggest that well designed games possess the potential to exert a positive impact on student engagement and motivation.

This outcome, however, hinges on the essential requisites that games align with learner needs and that the gameplay effectively mirrors the learning objectives integral to the program. This holistic perspective underscores the complex dynamics of game design, learning goals, and student motivation within the landscape of educational innovation.

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Annex 1 - Information sheet

Information Sheet – (July 2023)	
Title of research project - UPSKILLS - Insights into the effects of games in learning	
Purpose of the research study	
<p>The UPSKILLS project is an Erasmus+ strategic partnership for higher education that seeks to identify and tackle the gaps and mismatches in digital skills for linguistics and language students through the development of a new curriculum component and supporting materials to be embedded in existing programmes of study. To this end, we are investigating how the use of games and gamification can be used as a supporting method to engage students with the proposed curricular content.</p> <p>This focus group is being used as part of data collection for the UPSKILLS project. It is aimed towards students of languages and linguistics who are participating in the UPSKILLS summer school.</p>	
Lead Researcher	Vanessa Camilleri
What will be required from you during the experiment/study	
<p>You will be given a short survey to complete. The purpose of this survey is to collect your insights and thoughts about games and game-based learning, and your perceptions about the effectiveness of games to engage you with academic content. Following this survey, you may be asked to participate in a 1 hour focus group. During this focus group session some questions will be asked to understand better what were the strengths and the weaknesses of using games for learning.</p>	
Time required	
Interview: 45-60 minutes	
Risks and benefits	

Risks: By participating in this study you will not be exposing yourself to any specific risks.

Benefits: By participating in this study you will be contributing to research that may serve to strengthen the teaching and learning methods of Linguistics courses.

Confidentiality and participation

Your personal identity will only be known to the lead researcher. Your name and other personal information will **not** be published in the research results. Your personal opinions will be published, but they will **in no way** be associated with your identity.

Participation in this study is voluntary, and does not in any way impact your physical/mental/emotional health. There is no remuneration for the study.

How to withdraw from the study

Kindly note that you are free to ask to stop the interview at any time. If you choose to do so, kindly inform the lead researcher throughout the interview.

If you have any questions about this study, please contact:

Email: vanessa.camilleri@um.edu.mt

Annex 2 - Consent form

Consent Form – July 2023	
Title of research project - UPSKILLS - Insights into the effects of games in learning	
Lead Researcher	Vanessa Camilleri
Participant identification number for this study:	
Kindly tick (✓) the boxes to confirm you consent to participating in this study	
<p>1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated (<i>July2023</i>) explaining the research project and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project.</p> <p>2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw it any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. Furthermore, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline.</p> <p>3 I agree for the data collected from me to be used in future research.</p> <p>4 I agree to take part in the above research project.</p>	
Signatures	
<p>_____</p> <p>Name of participant</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Signature</p> <p>_____</p> <p>Date</p>	

Annex 3 - Post game survey tool questions

UPSKILLS Game Survey

The UPSKILLS project is an Erasmus+ strategic partnership for higher education that seeks to identify and tackle the gaps and mismatches in digital skills for linguistics and language students through the development of a new curriculum component and supporting materials to be embedded in existing programmes of study. To this end, we are investigating how the use of games and gamification can be used as a supporting method to target skills gaps and address industry and societal needs.

This survey is being used as part of data collection for the UPSKILLS project. It is aimed towards students of languages and linguistics who have used any of the suggested games in the UPSKILLS curriculum. It should not take more than 10-15 minutes to complete.

Further information about the project can be found at <https://upskillsproject.eu/>. If you have questions about this survey, please contact Dr Vanessa Camilleri from the University of Malta at vanessa.camilleri@um.edu.mt.

The information provided by you in this questionnaire will be used for research purposes. It will not be used in a manner which would allow the identification of your individual responses. Anonymised research data will be archived in order to make it available to other researchers in UPSKILLS in line with current data sharing practices.

I give my consent to participate in this study. I understand that participation in this study is on a voluntary basis and that I can withdraw from this study, without any consequences, at any point. *

Yes

No

Next

Clear form

Demographics

Gender *

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

Age

Choose ▼

Country of Residence *

Choose ▼

University/Course *

Your answer _____

Use of Games *

- I have used games as part of my University course
- I have used games through my participation in the UKSKILLS Summer School
- I have opted out of playing games for learning
- Other: _____

Back

Next

Clear form

Games & Learning

This section will focus on the usage of the game, your own motivation in playing the game and the engagement, if any, which you feel the game has stimulated.

Which game did you play? (if you have played more than one game you are asked * to choose one and focus the rest of your answers to describe this one game)

Your answer _____

How many times did you play this game? *

- 1-3 times
- 4-6 times
- More than 6 times

How long did each of these game sessions last? *

- 30 mins or less
- 30 mins to 1 hour
- 1-2 hours
- More than 2 hours

Have you reached the completion of the game?

- Yes
- No

Think of one game that you played as part of your course. How would you rate your experience in terms of:

	Extremely bad	Bad	Neutral	Good	Extremely good
The game was quite entertaining and fun to play	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I played the game only because it was obligatory	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

I believe more time was needed to play the game	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The game was related directly to the course I am studying for	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The game was related indirectly to the course I am studying for	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The game is relevant to the profession of the language specialist	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The game made me think about aspects of the language specialist profession	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Through the game I feel that I have improved some of the aspects of the learning material we covered in class	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Through the game I feel that I know more about the content covered in the course	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
After playing the game I decided I needed to know more about the subject	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Back

Next

Clear form

Games & Design

Briefly describe the game you played

Your answer _____

The following questions relate to the design of the game

	True	False	Does not apply
The game was easy to learn and play	☐	☐	☐
The game was too simple	☐	☐	☐
I felt that the game did not provide any fun or excitement	☐	☐	☐
The graphics of the game enticed me to play more	☐	☐	☐
The narrative of the game motivated me in completing the game	☐	☐	☐
The game provided a way of testing my knowledge of the subject	☐	☐	☐
The game provided entertainment and was fun to use	☐	☐	☐
I believe the game decreased some of the monotony of lectures	☐	☐	☐

Playing the game helped me identify issues which I didn't pick up during lectures

The game's narrative and rules of play made it more interesting and fun

What changes would you propose to improve the overall experience of playing the game?

Your answer

Would you recommend this game to other students? Why or why not?

Your answer

Back

Next

Clear form

Annex 4 - Focus group interview questions

Title: Exploring Games in Higher Education: Fostering Motivation and Engagement

Introduction:

“Good afternoon, everyone! Thank you all for being here today. My name is Vanessa Camilleri - I am from the University of Malta, more specifically I lecture at the Department of Artificial Intelligence, and I'm quite excited to facilitate this focus group session on the topic of 'Exploring Games in Higher Education: Fostering Motivation and Engagement.' Your participation in this discussion is very valuable, and we appreciate your time and insights.

Purpose of the Focus Group:

Today, we are here to explore the use of games and gamified elements in higher education and their impact on student motivation and engagement. As we know, education is constantly evolving, and the integration of technology and innovative teaching methods, such as games, has become an exciting area of exploration.

Confidentiality and Consent:

Before we proceed, I want to assure you that your participation and responses will be kept strictly confidential. We will not share any identifying information outside of this focus group. Additionally, your participation in this session is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw at any point without any consequences.

Semi-Structured Format:

This focus group will follow a semi-structured format, which means that while I have prepared some questions to guide our discussion, I also encourage open and spontaneous conversations. Feel free to share your personal experiences, thoughts, and opinions on the topic. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in hearing diverse perspectives.

Respectful and Inclusive Discussion:

Let's create an atmosphere of respect and inclusivity, where everyone's voice is valued. Please feel free to build on each other's responses and engage in constructive discussions. If anyone feels uncomfortable or wants to add something later, there will be opportunities for follow-up after the session as well.

Recording:

To ensure we capture all the valuable insights accurately, we will be recording this focus group session. The recordings will be used for research purposes only and will be securely stored.

Time Frame:

We anticipate this session to last approximately 1 hour. We will aim to cover all the questions, but we might also adapt the discussion based on the depth and richness of your responses.

Icebreaker/Introductions:

To start off, let's do a quick round of introductions. Please share your name, academic background, and any experiences you've had with games or gamified learning in higher education. This will help us get to know each other a bit better before we delve into the discussion.

Wrap-up:

At the end of the session, we will summarise the key insights and conclusions. Additionally, if you have any further thoughts or wish to provide additional feedback, you can share them either in this session or reach out to us later.

Thank you again for participating in this focus group. Your input will contribute to a better understanding of the role of games in higher education and how they impact student motivation and engagement. Let's now begin our exploration and discussion!"

Questions

- A. What is your experience with using games or gamified elements in higher education? Have you encountered any specific games or gamified learning activities during your academic journey?
- B. How do you perceive the impact of games on motivation and engagement in the learning process? Can you recall any specific instances where games or gamified elements helped you stay motivated or engaged in a course?
- C. In your opinion, what are the key factors that make games effective tools for stimulating motivation in higher education? Conversely, what limitations or challenges do you see in their use?
- D. Are there any particular game mechanics or features that you find particularly effective in fostering engagement and motivation? How do these mechanics differ from traditional teaching methods?
- E. Do you believe that the use of games in higher education can lead to better learning outcomes? Why or why not? Can you provide examples to support your view?

- F. How do you think games can be integrated into the curriculum without compromising the core academic content? What subjects or topics do you think can benefit the most from gamified approaches?
- G. Are there any concerns or reservations you have about the use of games in higher education? For instance, do you worry about the potential for distraction or the risk of prioritizing entertainment over learning?
- H. What role do you think instructors and educators should play in implementing games in the classroom? How can they ensure a balanced and effective use of games for educational purposes?
- I. Have you experienced any instances where the use of games in higher education positively influenced collaboration and teamwork among students? Can you share those experiences?
- J. Some argue that games might lead to superficial learning or limited transfer of knowledge to real-world scenarios. What are your thoughts on this matter, and how can this concern be addressed?
- K. How do you believe the use of games impacts students with different learning styles? Do you think certain students might benefit more from gamified approaches, while others might struggle?
- L. What kind of support or resources do you think would be helpful for instructors who want to incorporate games into their teaching methods? What training or professional development opportunities would be beneficial?
- M. Are there any specific types of games or genres that you believe are better suited for higher education? Why do you think these particular games are more suitable than others?
- N. In your experience, do you find that games in higher education have influenced your critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, or creativity? How have they impacted your approach to learning?
- O. Finally, if you could design an ideal game-based learning experience for a specific higher education course, what would it look like? What elements would you incorporate to ensure maximum motivation and engagement?

Note to Educators wishing to repurpose these questions for their own research:

Remember to adapt and tailor these questions to the specific context of your focus group and their experiences with games in higher education. Additionally, leave room for follow-up questions to delve deeper into participants' responses and to encourage meaningful discussions during the focus group interview.